

FROM FRUSTRATION TO PUBLICATION: SUPPORTING STUDENTS IN WRITING SCIENTIFIC ARTICLES

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Abstract

Writing articles is an obligation that must be done by a student to complete his studies at university. However, their ability to write quality articles is still low so they find it difficult to publish their articles in good journals. This study aims to reveal what obstacles students have in the process of writing articles. This research uses a qualitative approach and by using phenomenological methods. Researchers conducted interviews with 6 students to explore data about their obstacles in writing articles. The data that has been successfully collected is analyzed using Colaizzi data processing techniques. The study's findings identified five key themes that proved to be challenges for students trying to write papers, 1. Their willingness to learn to write articles is still low; 2. Do not have a laptop; 3. Do not know how to write articles; 4. do not know how to find references; and 5. Don't know how to avoid a high degree of similarity in writing. It is hoped that the findings of this study will influence future university policies to ensure that students receive adequate training in article writing so they can create and publish their work in reputable journal.

Keywords: Writing Articles, Article Publication, Students' Obstacle.

INTRODUCTION

The publication of scientific articles has a very important role in Education, with the publication of research results conducted by researchers in this case including students, the development of science can be accessed by everyone (Ildil et al., 2023) (Situmorang et al., 2023). Results of previous studies (Neogi & Partap, 2021) shows that 55% of the purpose of people visiting the library is to find references to other people's publications for writing their articles. Students should spend a lot of their time in the library because they can access information sources both from books and online journals there, this will certainly greatly help them in writing articles (Iqbal & Shahzad, 2021) (Yagnasridevi & Jeysankar, 2019). The publication of the latest research results will help others who want to update their knowledge about a field of science, by continuing to monitor and follow the latest scientific developments, an expert in a field of science will continue to have the latest science (Samala et al., 2023). Publication of research results should be done by every researcher, this is important because if the latest study results are not published then other people who have interest in the field of science do not get the latest information (Magee, 2019). Research results that are only displayed in library cabinets will certainly have less usefulness, because they can only be read by people around the library, but if the research results are published *online* through an *open journal system* or a journal *website*, people who are far from the library if they have an internet network will be able to read the latest findings from

the research conducted. Publication of research results that are read by many people may be a reference for future research, research results that get many citations mean that the research carried out is meaningful to others, the more citations it will show that the person who did the research has a good reputation in the eyes of other researchers (Bilalli et al., 2021) (Rahardja et al., 2019). The results of research produced by researchers sometimes do not always have a high level of credibility, because it is suspected that there are researchers who are rather excessive in interpreting the meaning of their research results and use inappropriate methods (Girault, 2022)

Publication of scientific articles that will have a good impact on universities. Universities that have a high level of publication can be interpreted as the campus has superior productivity in developing science, therefore students and lecturers must continue to be encouraged to be able to produce quality publications in reputable international journals as much as possible (Panjaitan et al., 2021) (Garfield, 2006). Higher education as a gathering place for academics, experts, and students who will each complete their studies are required to conduct research and should continue to produce the latest research findings in various fields of science on the campus. The progress of a nation can be seen from the progress of research carried out in universities and other institutions. If the research is many and good, it will certainly greatly contribute to various sectors in the country (Sukardi et al., 2023). However, if the research carried out is not of high quality and only a little, the impact that will be caused will also definitely be small so the changes and development of the nation will grow slowly (Van Wesel, 2016) (L. Allen et al., 2009) (Green & Baskind, 2007). Moreover, the trend of writing articles with the number of authors of one person has also decreased by ten percent, and authors have begun to make collaborative efforts in conducting research and writing articles for the publication of their research results (Maltseva & Batagelj, 2022)

The latest policy development requires students to have skills in writing good articles. This is very much needed so that the articles they make can be published in their destination journals (Iftanti, 2016). Scientific articles are a form of student writing that contains scientific elements, this work is not made using narrative sentences that do not have a good argumentation basis but the writing must have references as a foundation in developing narratives in the article (Sandoval & Millwood, 2005). Scientific articles must also be made with good grammar so that readers can easily understand what ideas the author wants to convey, The author must also pay attention to the title and abstract because it is the main concern of readers when looking at an article, therefore the author must make an interesting title and abstract (Goyal & Santhanam, 2022).

The demand to publish scientific articles for lecturers and students has affected increasing the number of studies (Vinkler, 2013) (Fernandes & Monteiro, 2017). The government and universities began to set the requirement to be able to complete studies for students to have a publication. This invites various responses for students, some feel this is not a problem but some consider this as a new obstacle to being able to quickly get a bachelor's, master's, or even doctoral degree, so it is not unusual if some students diplomas still cannot be graduated because there is no publication owned by students (Pezzoni et al., 2016). Students who realize that they have to try on their own to find out how to write articles will sometimes also ask librarians on their campus to solve the problems they face, so librarians must also have knowledge about the world of publications so that they can tell what students should do in making articles

and searching for references in the library (Martin et al., 2022). In the same line, experimental study also revealed that students' ability to write articles is still weak, both in the title and in other parts of the article, so training needs to be done to improve their ability to write articles (Nandiyanto & Azizah, 2022). Moreover, The importance of writing articles is also felt by health scientists, but they tend to be less willing to do it because of their lack of time to learn how to write articles and other supporting publication problems (Galanis, 2012). Article writing is not only done by ordinary students, evidence shows that students who have autism are actually better at writing articles because they are more perfectionist-minded, when compared to normal students, their article quality is poorer (Gillespie-Lynch et al., 2020). An experimental study reported that students and teachers also experience obstacles in writing, so it needs to be treated by giving assignments in a disciplined manner by reading and then writing down the important points base on in the reading material (Wissinger & De La Paz, 2020). In addition, Compiling a paragraph that has a strong argument and is supported by strong references is also an obstacle for students in Spain because it is rarely taught directly by lecturers (Luna et al., 2020). Furthermore, a research indicates that students feel anxiety in writing, this is caused by not understanding the English they use in writing, in addition the lack of experience in writing practice also makes students anxious when writing article (Rabadi & Rabadi, 2020).

From several previous studies that have been conducted by several researchers, it is clear that there has been no research that seeks to explore data qualitatively about what difficulties are felt by students in writing articles, therefore this study aims to identify what are the obstacles for students in writing scientific articles. This research is very necessary to do because it will be useful for policy makers at universities so that they know what are the obstacles for students in writing articles which are one of the requirements for graduating as an undergraduate.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

This study used a qualitative design and used phenomenological approach. The purpose of this study is to find out what are the inhibiting factors for students in writing articles which is one of the requirements required by universities so that students are entitled to hold a bachelor's degree.

All informants involved in the research were students from the Faculty of Sports Science, Universitas Negeri Padang, researchers randomly selected 2 students from the sports education department, 2 students from the coaching department, and 2 students from the health and recreation department so that the total number of informants in this study was 6 people (Gender: male=3, female=3; Age: male=22, 67±0, 58, female=22, 33±0, 58). All informants are undergraduate students who are preparing their articles as one of the requirements to obtain a bachelor's degree at Universitas Negeri Padang. The informants interviewed were students who had finished taking courses in research methodology, statistics and had also finished conducting research for their thesis. They are students from the entrance year starting from 2017, 2018, and 2019. However, their experience in making articles published in national and international journals has not existed at all.

The instrument used in this study is that the researcher alone. The data collection process in this study used the help of recording tools, field notes, and a list of questions that had been designed before the interview was conducted.

Examples of questions asked in this study are "What do you know about scientific articles?", "What are the steps in writing scientific articles?", "What are some difficulties you feel in writing scientific articles?" Data collection begins by looking for data related to students who will graduate in March 2023 at Universitas Negeri Padang. Data on students who will graduate are obtained from the secretary of the sports education department, the secretary of the coaching department, and the secretary of the health and recreation department. After the names of the students are obtained, the researcher randomly chooses a male and a female student from each department and then contact and ask related to their willingness to become informants in the research to be carried out. Researchers invited 2 students from each department who agreed to become informants to conduct interviews one by one in a room. The interview process was conducted for approximately 90 minutes for all informants with an average of 15 minutes per person. Researchers record the interview process so that the information can be re-extracted for data analysis purpose.

The data is analyzed with Colaizzi data processing techniques (Polit & Beck, 2010). The data analysis used in this study is thematic analysis, this analysis is usually used to describe and identify and group themes that appear as information provided by informants when interviews are conducted (Nowell et al., 2017). This thematic analysis can also see similarities and differences in informant answers which is useful for categorizing themes (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The researcher then rewrites the answers given by the informant into Microsoft Word so that the sentence or phrase can be coded for in-depth analysis. Furthermore, sentences or phrases that have the same concept will be grouped into a certain theme.

RESULTS

There are five themes that emerged as a result of this study, while the five themes are as follows.

Theme 1: Lack of Willingness to Learn

The response from participants shows that the willingness to learn writing articles independently is still low for students, amid current technological advances and the many interesting games on their *mobile phones* that can be accessed at any time have diverted the attention of students to read books. The presence of games that attract students and coupled with their less academic environment has resulted in their interest in learning being distracted by things that related to games. In addition, the sports activities they do with friends are also a diversion factor in learning new knowledge. The following are excerpts from interviews with participants.

"... But because of the will from the heart that is still lacking, there are still many other activities that are more comfortable to do, as a sports student, doing physical exercise and various other activities to fill spare time". (P1)

"... Lack of reading and also lack of looking for information, lack of interest in asking questions, sir". (P2)

"... Indeed, during the lecture it had not been taught, but my interest in learning independently about how to write articles was also low at that time, Sir, because it was not a subject that had exams and also did not know why should i learn it, but at the end of graduation day I just knew that one of the requirements was to make an article and it made me confused about where to start". (P5)

Theme 2: Do not have a Laptop

The absence of laptops owned by students is an obstacle for some respondents, this is because to type articles anytime and anywhere students certainly need a personal laptop, if they do not have a laptop then they are forced to go to internet cafes or borrow friends' laptops to use alternately. But some respondents think that it is not a significant obstacle for them to be able to continue learning. The following is an excerpt from interviews with respondents.

“... The first one is actually no laptop sir, the second is probably the biggest one now there is no laptop actually can go to an internet café or something, well on HP you can also.” (P1)

“if I still find it difficult to make the article because there is no laptop yet, Sir, if you want to make having to go to a friend's boarding house is a bit heavy, especially until there the laptop is also being used with him, so it is even more discouraged for me Sir, or going to a computer rental place sometimes it feels uncomfortable for a long time there because it is hot and the person is hemp so to concentrate on writing and issuing difficult ideas Sir. (P4)

“Hmm the problem may be because I don't have a laptop, Sir, so I decided to study independently at home. My friends who have laptops maybe they can watch you tube from home autodidact, and if I already have a laptop maybe I can also directly write the ideas I have directly. But if I don't have a laptop, I have to write first in a book and then borrow a friend's laptop to write the article, sometimes I feel uncomfortable borrowing friends' things for a long time. So the first problem for me is laptop Sir.” (P6)

Theme 3 No Knowledge of Article Writing Yet

In general, the respondents gave a response that did not know much about how to write scientific articles, they seemed confused to explain comprehensively about scientific articles, and how the steps of writing they did not know in detail. They seem to have never received material on how to write articles so their knowledge seems to be very minimal in that regard. The following are detailed excerpts from interviews with several respondents.

“I still don't know what a scientific article is and how to make it, I am still confused about the form of the structure.” (P6)

“Hmm the scientific article is a scientific work as far as I know, I have never made an article, so I still don't know how the steps for making it”. (P4)

“The scientific article is a summary of a study in its simple form, if in the bachelor degree is a thesis form, so the article is a summary form of research because I have never made it so I am confused to answer it, Sir. Lack of knowledge to create articles...” (P5)

“The scientific article is the result of your thesis, Sir, containing data on the results of our research, Sir. The step of making it is there is an abstract, the abstract contains conclusions from the background to the results of our research, Sir”. (P3)

“A scientific article is an idea or idea about a research Sir. The steps may be that we find out the problem first, or like we determine the title Sir, the title we will look for the problem first then we can conclude what we will make, then we can find the 5W 1H first then we can conclude the 5W 1H Sir. Then solving the problem, Sir”. (P2)

Theme 4 don't Know how to find References Yet

The response from some respondents also shows that they are still confused about finding the right reference to be used as a reference in the article they will make.

"... lack of knowledge to create articles, find the right references that can be used." (P5)

"... maybe in the discussion and also looking for references to it Sir." (P1)

"I still don't know how to find references to start writing Sir, so it is difficult to string words when writing, sometimes after reading the article we don't know what we want to write and still doubt the references are suitable or not for my article. " (P6)

Theme 5 High Level of Similarity

Plagiarism is also a difficult thing for students who are making articles because if it is not made using their own words, the level of similarity of writing with other writings will be high. Some respondents still do not know how to reduce the level of similarity so that their articles can be accepted by a journal.

"I yesterday after making the article kept checking the Turnitin was still high so I was asked to improve again and it made me overwhelmed to do what else to make the Turnitin low Sir." (P6)

"In my opinion, there is no need for Turnitin to be too rigid in assessing articles made by Sir, because I see words like table 1, for example, considered plagiarism, I am confused to replace with what other words, Sir, so as not to be detected plagiarism by Turnitin, and many more common sentences that are considered plagiarism by Turnitin, Sir, it is not fair". (P4)

"I feel annoyed by the Turnitin check, because I still don't understand the want of Turnitin, my friends say I have to paraphrase so that the Turnitin is low, but I haven't tried it so it hasn't known whether it works or I have to find another way to outsmart this Turnitin sir because it difficult for students, many friends are confused, maybe it is necessary to be taught how to write so that the article has a lower Turnitin score Sir." (P2)

DISCUSSION

There are five themes found in this research and will discuss below.

Lack of Willingness to Learn

The results of this study indicate that students' willingness to learn to write articles is still very low so that this is one of the reasons they are unable to produce quality articles. To be able to write quality articles, students must continue to learn and practice these skills consistently, because if they are not diligent in practicing, their writing skills will not improve (Gao et al., 2021). Experimental studies conducted by (Su et al., 2022) Revealing that to increase students' willingness to learn can be done by utilizing various technologies that exist today, lecturers should improve their abilities by learning the latest technology to support quality article writing. The use of technology when teaching will not only increase student willingness to learn but will also increase lecturer satisfaction in learning, as well as student final exam scores (Yang, 2020). Moreover, students have to read lot of literatures to get more insight when writing an article (Ramadhani & Zaim, 2023).

Do not have Laptop

Laptops have become an indispensable tool for writers, especially when it comes to writing articles. They offer portability, allowing writers to work from anywhere, whether they are in a coffee shop or on a plane. In addition, laptops come with pre-installed writing software, such as Microsoft Word or Google Docs, which provides an easy-to-use interface for creating and formatting articles (Juvonen et al., 2019). Moreover, laptops allow writers to easily edit and revise their articles, with tools such as cutting, copying, and pasting text, as well as formatting changes. This convenience and flexibility make laptops an essential tool for writers who want to create and refine their work efficiently. In summary, the role of laptops in writing articles cannot be overstated, as they provide a reliable and efficient platform for writers to create, edit, and refine their work (D. Allen & Connelly, 2016) (Orr, 2006). Internet access is another important feature of laptops that can aid writers in conducting research, fact-checking, and accessing online resources. Writing software also typically includes built-in tools for spell-checking and grammar correction, which can help writers to catch mistakes and improve the quality of their writing (Salvagno et al., 2023) (Warren et al., 2021).

Do not have a Knowledge about Writing Article

Writing scientific articles is still considered a difficult thing for students, this is because there is no good understanding of how concrete numbers are done to write the article. This is also found in studies conducted by (Rofiqo et al., 2018) which reveal that the level of understanding is the main reason why students find it difficult to produce a publication in the form of scientific articles. The ability of students to write articles in English form is an obstacle for them to write articles then coupled with the ability of lecturers to use technology to teach article writing is also still lacking so students do not get tools to write following the latest technological developments (Alharbi, 2021). One of the obstacles in writing this article can be overcome by applying cooperative learning, with this learning method, the ability of students to organize article content and the writing mechanism becomes better (Sunendar & Mulyati, 2019). A study (Ball, 2019) explained that giving modules to students can improve the ability to edit the articles they make, so this pattern can also be applied to improve students' ability to write.

Do not know how to Find Reference

The results showed that students' ability to find references to write articles is still a problem. The ability to search for articles which is the main source for article writing is a skill that must be mastered by article writers. Students and lecturers should be able to browse the main reading material and also be able to write it in different language styles (Hubbard & Dunbar, 2017). Studies conducted by (Bračanov et al., 2014) Explain that the references cited by students in making articles are accurate and appropriate.

In addition, the results of studies conducted by (Gallagher et al., 2023) Revealing that the trend of article citations used in article writing is getting newer and more and more, this is certainly a positive and enviable thing for other students. Students should seek help from their friends or lecturers if it is difficult to find references. Looking for an environment and friends who can help in writing is one of the solution that can be applied so that the article can be completed properly and on time (Affandi Arianto & Wulyani, 2022).

Do not know how to Decrease Similarity

The problem of plagiarism in writing articles carried out by students is fear, the issue of plagiarism is a classic issue and is commonly found in an article (Masic, 2013). Their understanding is still not good about how to avoid this when writing articles needs to be a serious concern for the campus so that they have a solution to the problem (Akbari, 2021). A study revealed that only 11.6% of students were able to detect plagiarism in their writing (Clarke et al., 2023). The ability of students to understand the substance of reading and rewrite it into the article they are making is still lacking, so this issue still exists today (Mukasa et al., 2023).

Turnitin is one of the tools that can be used to guarantee the originality of articles written by an author. Good writing must have a good level of uniqueness as well, therefore before publishing a written work you should check the similarity first (Mphahlele & McKenna, 2019). Turnitin can also be used by the campus to reduce plagiarism committed by students in making scientific papers (Dawson et al., 2020). The behavior to commit plagiarism has decreased When students know that their assignments or articles will be corrected using Turnitin by their lecturers, it is necessary to check the originality of the assignments done by students so that the tasks they make always have good quality and originality (Shang, 2019). Furthermore, a study explained that the existence of Turnitin managed by the university was unknown to its students and they were also confused in understanding the results of Turnitin (Alua et al., 2023). Knowledge and skills in writing with a low plagiarism rate must continue to be socialized to students and lecturers so that the quality of the articles produced is good (Chokoraia, 2023), Because the task of the campus is not only to teach students to be smart but also to teach them academic ethics (Toprak & Yücel, 2020). The problem of plagiarism can be reduced by using the problem-base learning method, a study explains that it can reduce the level of similarity of tasks given by lecturers (Ramdani et al., 2022). A good article will be easily accepted by a journal. Article writing must be made following the writing guidelines in a journal and be able to convince editors and reviewers who correct the article (Masic, 2018). The novelty of the research and the correctness of conducting research will greatly affect the acceptance of articles by journal managers. In addition, the articles created must also have a high level of originality and not a level of plagiarism. Up-to-date references are also needed to ensure that researchers are also people who keep up with the latest science. The results of the research conducted should be able to fill the gap that becomes void of ignorance of science (Nalliah & Rampal, 2021). The sample used in this study only came from one faculty in one of the universities in Indonesia so that the problems raised by students there may be different from the obstacles worries by students at other universities in the others country.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study show that students still have difficulties in writing articles. These obstacles are still their lack of willingness to learn to write articles, the absence of laptops they have, their lack of knowledge about how to write articles, their low ability to find quality references for their articles, and the high level of similarity of articles they make when checked using Turnitin. Further research should examine how lecturers' knowledge in making articles because it could be that not only students feel these obstacles but the difficulties are also felt by lecturers so they are not confident to teach it to students.

These existing weaknesses should be identified so that policymakers at the university level can provide appropriate solutions so that students are not constrained to complete their studies due to their lack of skills in the process of making scientific articles.

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